

Synthesis in the Pyridine Series. Part II.

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It has been observed by Mumm and Böhme (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 726) that though pyridines are readily obtained by reacting ethyl β -amino-crotonate with acyl pyruvic esters, the former fails to give pyridines when condensed with β -diketones or hydroxymethylene ketones. Contrary to this observation, one of us (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 289) has recently shown that the crotonic acid derivative readily condenses with hydroxymethylene ketones to give rise to various pyridine- β -carboxylates. Further as acetylacetoneamine, benzoyl-acetoneamine and diacetonitrile have also been found to react with hydroxymethylene-*cyclohexanone* to afford the formation of various *Bz-tetrahydroquinoline* derivatives (*cf.* Basu, *Annalen*, 1935, 514, 292), the above reaction might be considered to be a general one and consequently could be carried out with any tautomeric compound of the ketimine-enamine type on the one hand and a hydroxymethylene ketone on the other. With a view to establish the validity of the above statement and at the same time to find out a direct method for the synthesis of β -pyridylketones, the present investigation was mainly undertaken. It has now been found that ammonia derivative of acetylacetone, or that of benzoylacetone readily reacts with a hydroxymethylene ketone (I) to give rise to the pyridyl derivative (II) according to the scheme:

where R=alkyl or aryl group and R'=H or alkyl group.

Thus, on heating an equimolecular mixture of acetylacetoneamine and hydroxymethylene acetophenone in ethereal solution on a water-bath for several hours, 2-methyl-6-phenyl-3-acetylpyridine (II, R=Ph, R'=H) was isolated from the reaction mixture by first extracting

it with dilute hydrochloric acid and then neutralising the acid extract with sodium carbonate. Similarly the above amine gave 2-methyl-6-*p*-tolyl- and 2:5-dimethyl-6-ethyl-3-acetylpyridines when reacted respectively with hydroxymethylene methyl-*p* tolylketone and hydroxymethylene derivative of diethylketone. The corresponding 8-benzoylpyridines were again obtained by condensing the above hydroxymethylene ketones with benzoylacetoneamine.

All the β -pyridylketones described in the present paper are usually low melting colourless solids which are sparingly soluble in water but readily dissolve in ether, alcohol and other common organic solvents. They are tertiary bases and readily form hydrochlorides. In acid solution they give double salts with mercuric chloride and in alcoholic solution picrates with picric acid. The phenylketones differ from the methyl analogues with respect to their reactivity towards semicarbazide, as the former does not react whereas the latter readily gives the semicarbazones.

Certain pyridine bases, *e.g.*, 2:5:6-trimethyl-, 2:5-dimethyl-6-ethyl-, 2-methyl-6-*p*-tolylpyridines, have also been synthesised for the first time by lime distillation of their 3-carboxylic acids obtained in their turn by hydrolysing the respective condensation products of ethyl β -aminocrotonate with hydroxymethylene methylethylketone, hydroxymethylene diethylketone and hydroxymethylene methyl-*p*-tolylketone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acetyl Acetoneamine.

This was prepared by passing ammonia to acetylacetone according to Combes and Combes (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1893, *iii*, 7, 778) and obtained as a refracting liquid, *b. p.* 92°/14 mm. On cooling it set to a crystalline mass.

Condensation with hydroxymethylene acetophenone: Formation of 2-methyl-6-phenyl-3-acetylpyridine.—The hydroxymethylene ketone was prepared according to the method of Büllow and Sicherer (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 3891) and was preserved as its copper salt. It was freshly liberated from the above salt before use and was taken in ether. The ethereal solution was then heated under reflux with the required molecular quantity of acetylacetoneamine for about 16 hours. The solution became turbid owing to the separation of water. It was extracted with dilute hydrochloric acid (12 %) and the acid extract was

neutralised with sodium carbonate when the pyridine ketone slowly separated out as a low-melting solid. On crystallisation from dilute alcohol it melted at 90°, yield 50%. (Found: N, 6.75. $C_{14}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 6.63 per cent).

The pyridine ketone is insoluble in water, difficultly soluble in petroleum ether but easily dissolves in ether, alcohol and other common organic solvents.

The *hydrochloride*.—The base was dissolved in the minimum quantity of dilute hydrochloric acid (12 %) by warming, when on cooling crystals of the hydrochloride of 2-methyl-6-phenyl-3-acetylpyridine separated out, m.p. 143-44°. (Found: Cl, 14.30. $C_{14}H_{13}ON$, HCl requires Cl, 14.34 per cent).

The *picrate*.—The ketonic base was heated with an alcoholic solution of picric acid for a few minutes when on dilution with water the picrate of the base separated out. On recrystallisation from alcohol it was obtained in shining yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 166°. (Found: N, 12.60. $C_{20}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 12.72 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*.—A solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride on being neutralised with ammonia, was mixed with an alcoholic solution of the pyridine ketone. This was then heated under reflux on a water-bath for about 2½ hours; on dilution with water the semicarbazone of the acetylpyridine derivative separated out and was recrystallised from alcohol as long rectangular prisms, m.p. 212°. (Found: N, 21.19. $C_{15}H_{16}ON_4$ requires N, 20.89 per cent).

The *oxime*.—A solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride was neutralised with ammonia and heated with an alcoholic solution of the pyridine ketone for more than 5 hours on a water-bath. On diluting the reaction mixture with water, the oxime separated, which was obtained in microscopic needles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 106°. (Found: N, 12.62. $C_{14}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 12.38 per cent).

Condensation with hydroxymethylene methyl-p-tolylketone: Formation of 2-methyl-6-p-tolyl-3-acetylpyridine.—The hydroxymethylene compound, prepared by the method of Benary, Meyer and Charisius (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 106) was preserved as its sodium salt. An ethereal solution containing the molecular quantities of acetylacetoneamine and the above hydroxymethylene ketone, freshly liberated from its sodium salt, was refluxed for about 16 hours as in the previous case. On extracting the ethereal solution with dilute hydrochloric acid and neutralising the acid extract with sodium carbonate, the acetylpyridine derivative was isolated. It crystallised from dilute

alcohol in clusters of needles, melting at 78°. (Found: N, 6.34. $C_{15}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 6.20 per cent).

The *hydrochloride*, melts at 150-51°. (Found: Cl, 13.51. $C_{15}H_{15}ON$; HCl requires Cl, 13.58 per cent).

The *picrate* separated as yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 163-64°. (Found: N, 11.49. $C_{21}H_8O_8N_4$ requires N, 11.89 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was obtained as small needles from alcohol, m.p. 207°. (Found: N, 20.21. $C_{16}H_{18}ON_4$ requires N, 19.85 per cent).

The *oxime* separated as long shining needles from alcohol, m.p. 127°. (Found: N, 11.3. $C_{15}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 11.60 per cent).

Condensation of hydroxymethylene diethylketone: Formation of 2:5-dimethyl-6-ethyl-3-acetylpyridine.—An ethereal solution of hydroxymethylene derivative (11.3 g.), prepared according to the method of Claisen and Meyerowitz (*Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 3275), and acetylacetone-amine (9.8 g.) were heated under reflux as usual. On subsequent treatment of the reaction mixture, about 8 g. of the pyridine derivative were obtained, which when crystallised from boiling water melted at 60°. (Found: N, 7.97. $C_{11}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 7.90 per cent).

The *picrate* was obtained as yellow rhombic crystals, m.p. 118°. (Found: N, 13.99. $C_{17}H_{18}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.79 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in rectangular prisms, m.p. 201°. (Found: N, 24.29. $C_{12}H_{18}ON_4$ requires N, 23.90 per cent).

The *oxime* crystallised from alcohol (50%) in rectangular prisms, m.p. 128°. (Found: N, 14.96. $C_{11}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 14.58 per cent).

Benzoylacetoneamine.

The amine was prepared according to the method of Knoevenagel (*Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 2188) by passing ammonia to an alcoholic solution of benzoylacetone and was obtained in shining rhombic crystals, m.p. 143°.

Condensation with hydroxymethylene acetophenone: Formation of 2-methyl-6-phenyl-3-benzoylpyridine.—An ethereal solution of the hydroxymethylene ketone, freshly liberated from its sodium salt (10 g.), was mixed with an alcoholic solution of benzoylacetoneamine (8 g.) and the mixture was heated under reflux for more than 15 hours. The solution was then concentrated and treated with dilute hydrochloric

neutralised with sodium carbonate, when an oil was obtained. This was dissolved in ether and the ethereal solution was shaken with dilute hydrochloric acid. The acid extract was again neutralised with soda; when a solid separated out which crystallised from alcohol in prismatic plates, m.p. 77°. (Found: N, 5.25. $C_{19}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 5.13 per cent). It is soluble in ether, alcohol, etc., but insoluble in water. On heating with an alcoholic solution of picric acid the substance gave a picrate as tiny needles, m.p. 196° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 11.29. $C_{25}H_{18}O_8N_4$ requires N, 11.15 per cent). The phenylpyridineketone did not give any semicarbazone under the usual conditions.

Condensation with hydroxymethylene methyl-p-tolylketone: Formation of 2-methyl-6-p-tolyl-3-benzoylpyridine.—An equimolecular mixture of the above hydroxymethylene ketone and benzoylacetoneamine was heated in ether-alcoholic solution as in the previous case. On subsequent treatment the benzoylpyridine was easily isolated and was obtained in fine prisms after crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 84°. (Found: N, 5.11. $C_{20}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 4.88 per cent). Its picrate has already been described (cf. Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 289).

Ethyl β -Aminocrotonate.

Condensation with hydroxymethylene diethylketone: Formation of ethyl 2:5-dimethyl-6-ethylpyridine-3-carboxylate.—The hydroxymethylene derivative (17.0 g.) and the aminocrotonate (19.0 g.) in ethereal solution were heated under reflux for 15 hours. The reaction mixture on usual treatment, gave an oil (12.0 g.) which distilled at 145°/10 mm. (Found: N, 6.54. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 6.76 per cent).

It is a yellow refracting liquid, refractive index being 1.0005 at 39°. It is sparingly soluble in water but is easily miscible with all common organic solvents. With an alcoholic solution of picric acid it readily gives a picrate which crystallises from dilute alcohol in prisms, m.p. 120°. (Found: N, 12.39. $C_{18}H_{20}O_9N_4$ requires N, 12.8 per cent).

2:5-Dimethyl-6-ethylpyridine-3-carboxylic acid.—The above ethyl ester (5.5 g.) was heated under reflux with potassium hydroxide solution (15%, 25 c. c.) for more than one hour, and the solution filtered. The clear filtrate was made acid to Congo paper

with hydrochloric acid and the resulting solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue was extracted with absolute alcohol. The alcoholic solution (after charcoal treatment) was concentrated, cooled and diluted with ether, when the carboxylic acid separated out. This was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether (1:1) and obtained in clusters of needles, m.p. 193-94° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.54. $C_{10}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 7.82 per cent).

2:5-Dimethyl-6-ethylpyridine.—The above pyridine- β -carboxylic acid (1 part) was intimately mixed with finely powdered soda lime (about 3 parts) and the mixture was carefully heated under reduced pressure when an oil was obtained. This was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed and the liquid distilled as a colourless liquid at 181-82°/756 mm. (Found: N, 10.28. $C_9H_{13}N$ requires N, 10.37 per cent). It possesses a characteristic smell and gradually darkens in colour. With an alcoholic solution of picric acid it gave a *picrate* which crystallised from alcohol (50%) in prismatic yellow needles, m. p. 127°. (Found: N, 15.26. $C_{15}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 15.38 per cent).

2:5-Dimethyl-6-phenylpyridine.—2:5-Dimethyl-6-phenylpyridine-3-carboxylic acid (1 part) obtained from the condensation of ethyl β -aminocrotonate with hydroxymethylene ethylphenylketone (*cf.* Basu, *loc. cit.*), was intimately mixed with powdered soda lime (3 parts) and the mixture was heated under reduced pressure as in the previous case. The oil obtained was extracted with ether and finally distilled at 285-87°/758 mm. The *picrate* was obtained as fine needles from alcohol, m. p. 180°. (Found: N, 13.66. $C_{19}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 13.59 per cent). The pyridine derivative is thus found to be identical with that previously obtained by Scholtz (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1937).

2-Methyl-6-p-tolylpyridine.—2-Methyl-6-p-tolylpyridine-3-carboxylic acid (Basu, *loc. cit.*) was distilled with soda lime as in the previous cases and the oil obtained was distilled in *vacuo* at 291-92°/759 mm. as a colourless refracting liquid; refractive index is 1.5970 at 37.5°. The *picrate* crystallised from alcohol in long prismatic needles, m. p. 146°. (Found: N, 13.34. $C_{19}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 13.59 per cent).

2:5:6-Trimethylpyridine, obtained by the distillation of 2:5:6-trimethylpyridine-3-carboxylic acid (Basu, *loc. cit.*) with lime, distilled at 176-78°/759 mm. Echert and Lorica (*Monatsch.*, 1917,

38, 228) have isolated a similar pyridine base from coal tar and have recorded its boiling point as 173-74°/734 mm. and the m. p. of its picrate as 143-44°. The picrate of this product also melted at 144°. (Found: N, 16.10. $C_{14}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires N, 16.0 per cent).

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The Coagulation of Ferrocyanide Sols containing Varying Amounts of Potassium Ferrocyanide.

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The part played by the adsorption of constituent ions in determining the electrical charge of inorganic colloids is fairly understood. The relationship observed by Lottermoser (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1908, 62, 372) between the excess of the constituent ions present during the precipitation of similar halides and the sign of their charge find a simple explanation from the theoretical considerations of Mukherjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103) who pointed out the importance of the lattice forces in determining the nature of the primarily adsorbed layer on the surface. The electro-osmotic observations of Mukherjee and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924 31, 178; 1926, 3, 335, 371; 1927, 4, 459) support the theoretical considerations. The relative adsorbabilities of such ions have been discussed by them with reference to barium sulphate, lead chromate and silver halides. It has been found that associated with the primarily adsorbed layer there is often present a secondary adsorption of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions which lead respectively to the liberation of alkali and acid from the double decomposition of the reacting neutral salts. With increasing concentration of adsorbable ions having the same sign of charge as the surface, frequently the electrical charge increases to a maximum and then diminishes. In conformity to this, the stability of the colloidal solution under such conditions as measured by the coagulating concentrations of an electrolyte has also often been found to pass through a maximum. The stability of a sol and